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THE USE OF CYNARA SCOLYMUS FOR THE TREATMENT OF DISEASES OF THE HEPATOBILIARY SYSTEM

Summary.

The article discusses biologically active components of artichoke (Cynara scolymus) and their effect on the human body. Medicinal plants are actively used in the modern world, both in traditional and in alternative therapy. This highlights the importance of developing research that covers not only the effective use of medicinal plants, but also their conservation and sustainable development of their populations. To solve this problem, in-depth scientific research is needed, aimed at analyzing the state of the main medicinal plants in different regions and the conditions of their growth

Key words *cynara scolymus, biologically active substances, biochemical characteristics*

Introduction Spiny artichoke (*Cynara scolymus* L.) is a perennial herb native to Ethiopia, but also grows in the Mediterranean and South America. Artichoke was known several thousand years before our era. This plant was grown in ancient Egypt and Greece. In Rome, it was believed that artichoke cleanses the body, freshens the breath and even prevents baldness. During the Renaissance and the Middle Ages, artichoke was used as a choleric, antirheumatic, and diuretic agent.[1,2]

Research materials and methods. The material of our research is the introduction of the herb *cynara scolymus* for the treatment of diseases of the hepatobiliary system. *Cynara scolymus* has a rich chemical composition that makes it a valuable medicinal plant. The prophylactic effect of artichoke is due to the presence in it of a complex of biologically active substances contained in the leaves of *cynara scolymus*. Cynarin, together with phenolic acids, bioflavonoids and other components, provides choleric, diuretic and hepatoprotective effects, helps reduce the level of urea in the blood and improves metabolic processes in the body. In addition, artichoke contains flavonoids, bitter substances, ascorbic acid, vitamins B1 and B2, carotene, inulin, as well as minerals, in particular potassium salts. The main components of artichoke include: cynarin - a biologically active compound that gives artichoke its choleric properties; flavonoids - have antioxidant properties; caffeic acid - known for its anti-inflammatory effect; chlorogenic acid - also has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties; inulin - a natural polysaccharide that promotes healthy intestinal microflora; mucilaginous substances - help calm the gastrointestinal tract; vitamins - especially rich in B vitamins (B1, B2, B3, B5, B6) and vitamin C; minerals - calcium,

magnesium, potassium, phosphorus, iron and zinc. Artichoke also contains: essential oils, sterols, terpenoids, lactones, proteins and amino acids.[3,4,5]

Dried or fresh artichoke leaves are mainly used to prepare decoction or tincture from artichoke. Wash fresh or dry leaves in a container and add water in a ratio of 1:10 (1 part of artichoke leaves is added for every 10 parts of water). Bring to a boil and cook for about 20-30 minutes. Insist for 10-15 minutes, strain and can be taken. Take 1/2 or 1/3 cup before meals 2-3 times a day.

Cynara scolymus L helps restore the functional state of the liver and biliary tract, and also normalizes the work of the gastrointestinal tract. It has hepatoprotective, diuretic and antioxidant properties. This complex of useful substances determines its use in medicine to support liver health, improve digestion, lower cholesterol and support the immune system.

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